

ASSESSMENT OF IMMUNOLOGICAL REACTIVITY IN BLEEDING COMPLICATIONS OF GASTRIC AND DUODENAL ULCERS AND ITS CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Urgency: Gastric and duodenal ulcers, when complicated by bleeding, are still an urgent problem of emergency gastroenterology and surgery. In such cases, along with morphological changes, impaired immunological reactivity also plays an important role in the development of the disease. In experimentally formed gastric ulcers, an almost twofold decrease in the total number of thymocytes was observed, which is mainly explained by the effect of stress. Under the influence of stress factors, the number of cells in the lymph nodes, bone marrow (bone marrow) and thymus decreases significantly. Also, negative changes are observed in the processes of rosette formation and anti-tellogenesis.

The aim of the study was to evaluate immunological parameters in the context of bleeding complications of ulcer disease and to determine their clinical significance.

Materials and methods . Based on clinical observations, 34 patients with ulcerative colitis complicated by bleeding were analyzed. 25 almost healthy donors (residents of Bukhara) were involved as controls. Immune status was assessed by blood tests and indicators of T- and B-lymphocyte subpopulations. During the analysis of the immune status (according to 4–7 main indicators), secondary immunodeficiency was detected in all patients with gastric and duodenal ulcers complicated by bleeding. According to the results of the study, a significant decrease in the number of lymphocytes, T-lymphocytes and T-helper cells was observed against the background of bleeding. At the same time, an increase in the number of T-cytotoxic cells, a decrease in the immune regulation index, and an increase in the level of CD95 antibodies (FAS/APO-1 antigen) were noted.

Also, a decrease in the number of CD4 (T-helper) cells and a relative increase in CD8 (T-cytotoxic) cells indicated an imbalance in the immune system. A decrease in the CD4/CD8 index means that immunological reactivity can weaken the body's resistance to infections, with complications such as bleeding.

Thus, the changes observed in lymphocyte and T-cell subpopulations can be considered as important immunological indicators that aggravate the clinical condition of patients with bleeding complications from gastric and duodenal ulcers.

Results. According to the results of the study, a number of changes in immunological reactivity were observed in ulcer disease with bleeding complications. In particular, a decrease in the number of T-helper and B-lymphocytes, an imbalance in T-suppressor activity, and changes in immunoglobulin concentrations (decreased IgG and IgA levels, relative increase in IgM) were noted. In some patients, secondary immunodeficiency occurred, which increased the risk of recurrent bleeding and severe course. Against the background of T-cell deficiency, the relative amount of B-lymphocytes was within the normal range in 17.7% of patients, and the absolute number was found to be high due to leukocytosis.

The indicators of the natural defense system also changed: the number of natural killer cells (CD16+ cells) increased by 17.2%, but in 29.4% of cases, a decrease in the phagocytic activity of neutrophils was observed. This indicates an imbalance in the body's ability to resist infection.

Conclusion. Evaluation of immunological parameters in bleeding complications of gastric and duodenal ulcers is of clinical importance. Impaired immunological reactivity can be used as an additional criterion in assessing the severity of the disease, prognosis and treatment tactics. Therefore, it is advisable to introduce immunological analyses into practice in such patients

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